

Adult Obesity in Columbus Ohio

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Introduction

This paper is aim to discuss and emphasize on the adult obesity issues in Columbus, Ohio state. Overweight and obesity are defined as abnormal and excessive body fat, which can lead to different types of diseases. The seriousness of this epidemic issue in Ohio State can be seen by looking t the report of the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention which state more than 34.9% of Americans in the United States are considered obese. In Ohio, approximately 30.4% of the population is considered obese (Centers for Disease Control 2014).

Discussion

Obesity among aduts in ohio is a syndrome with proven physical, psychological and social implications. Currently, there is strong evidence that obesity associated with a higher prevalence of chronic diseases such as cardiovascular disease, some cancers, diabetes, joint problems etc, constituted as a major risk factor in adulthood processes. Changes in obesity among aduts has changed dramatically over past 30 years. The obesity epidemic affects, especially in aduts, in which the rate of increase in prevalence are higher than those of adolescents in Columbus Ohio (Hamilton, 2014).

Today our general public in Columbus Ohio is continually encompassed by fast paced lives and occupied calendars that the food industries eat these regular battles of caught up with working men and ladies by taking the activity to make their lives less demanding with unhealthy fast foods at a low cost. Americans in Ohio state are not watching what they eat and don't put attention on their daily calorie intake and portion control. Consumers in Ohio sate are spending

\$1.6 million per year on potato chips, and \$3.5 billion a year on unnecessary sweets (Black, 2014). About 46% of Americans in Ohio State eat out every night, and one-third of them choose to eat fast food. The desire of junk food is replacing the need for fruits and vegetables and this is contributing to obesity in such a big way. When you go buy groceries, there is unhealthy choices everywhere you turn, and it seems that Americans are looking for convenience, and it's more convenient to buy a 5 minute microwavable pizza at frozen food aisle then to actually make a balanced meal at home (Hamilton, 2014).

According to Healthy People 2020 (2014), the goal for nutrition and weight status is to promote health and to reduce chronic disease through consuming healthy foods and achieving and maintaining healthy body weights. The Nutrition and Weight Status recommendation eight (NSW-8) has created the goal of a 10% improvement of healthy body weight by 2020. Ohio has not met this goal.

Causes of Obesity Adult in Columbus Ohio

Adult Obesity among black population in Ohio Sate is because of a complex and multifactorial disease resulting from the interaction of genetic and environmental factors, mediated by social, economic, endocrine, metabolic and psychiatric conditions. African Americans in the State of Ohio have an average obesity rate of 36.0%. Among non-hispanic black women, the obesity is significantly higher with an rate of 56.6%. In Ohio State black people are more prone to obesity as compare to white people. According to Ohio Department of Healths vital statistics (2014), approximately 26,072 citizens died from preventable heart disease. According to the American Heart Association, obesity significantly increases the risk of heart disease and mortality (American Heart Association, 2014). Environmental factors are linked to

lifestyle, such as eating high calorie diets and sedentary lifestyle (Black, 2014). Specific treatments and surgical procedures have been successfully performed in the different clinic of Ohio State, generating satisfactory results with patients and specialists in Adult Obesity (Hamilton, 2014).

Conclusion

Promoting healthy diets and regular physical activity are essential in the fight against adulthood obesity epidemic. Adult Obesity is a serious problem and should be taken with utmost attention in Columbus Ohio. The sooner the Adult Obesity is treated, the greater the chances of control.

References

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